

Summary

Debate topic statement: **Divorce should be banned**

Outline: Pro

Argument #1 Orphanhood

It is observed that orphanhood is one of the consecutive reasons why we should ban divorce. In fact, according to Woodruff (2019), developed countries' apprehension of orphanages is obsolete long ago. Currently, in developing countries orphanages are housing a significant number of children. Actually, the majority of children in orphanages have one or both parents alive. Undoubtedly, not in all cases parents had financial or other difficulties. However, nowadays people are facing situations where children are in orphanage because of parental divorce or for other reasons and none of parents keeps the children with them. It is followed that a huge number of children are facing disaffects and risks for successful future just because of not significantly thought decision of couples.

- **Warrant (evidence)**

According to UNICEF.org in 2015, globally as a child under the age of 18, 140 millions of children are housed by orphanages and Asian countries include 61 millions of orphans. Unfortunately, 95 percent of all orphans are under the age of 5. Surely, not all of the orphans lost their both parents due to the deaths, but also in many cases children in orphanages have one parent or surviving both of them. From nearly 140 million of orphans only 15.1 million have lost their both parents. It is clear that the remaining 124.9 million of them have both or one parent. Locally it is not accepted too. According to CABAR.asia In Uzbekistan only 16% of children in orphanage lost their parents because of deaths and 10% in because of deprivation of parental rights in 2020. Remaining 74% children handed over to the orphanage because of not well decided decisions of couples having a chance to divorce in unexpected problems and create new family.

- **Impact (why this matter)**

It is an undeniable fact that usually orphans and children who live with their parents have significant differences in their behavior and in other cases. It is not a secret that parents do a lot than providing

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children with food, housing and supporting themselves financially. In fact, according to Hamilton's article in 2014 including Nelson's research, parents play a crucial role in children's brain development. Actually, Nelson believes that most children who live in orphanages have difficulties with mental and emotional growth. Also, Nsabimana E, Rutembesa E, Wilhelm P and Martin-Soelch C (2019) found that considering whether children were orphans or not, they found that institutionalization and absence of orphans were independently associated with higher rates of externalized behavioral problems. Thus, children placed in specialized institutions, although their fathers and mothers were alive, had the most pronounced behavioral problems. This suggests that children who are not orphans are more vulnerable to the adverse effects of institutionalization than orphans. On the other hand, orphans who lived in a family environment had the least externalizing behavioral problems.

Argument #2. Negative effect on children's psychology

Nowadays, a huge amount of children whose parents are divorced are having a negative impact on their psychology. It is not a secret that children are suffering because of the not significant decision of their parents. Though this tendency has been documented in many studies, the explanation for this phenomenon remains elusive. Some children don't find the separation of the parents the hardest part to cope with, in fact, some find that the most difficult part when it comes to dealing with divorce is the stress that accompanies it. A lot of stressful, inconvenient situations may drop in their laps such as changing schools, moving or changing homes and living with one parent who is more high-strung now with more responsibility, and lack of appearances from the other. This stress can greatly affect the child's mental health. According to previous research, children with divorced parents, when compared with continuously married parents report greater unhappiness, less satisfaction with life, a weaker sense of personal depression and a greater use of mental health services. The worst thing is that they may become merciless. It may cause many problems as a root.

- **Warrant (Evidence)**

In fact, According to Davies and Cummings (2004), children from divorced families may face psychological problems by disrupting parent-child relationships. In 2007 Meadows, McLahan and Brooks-Gunns proved that divorce affects child behavior problems as depression and

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anxiety. Furthermore another research conducted by Nievar and Luster in 2006 showed that divorce impacts child's psychological distress, family income and children's outcomes in early and middle childhood

- **Impact. Why does this matter?**

Banning parental divorce is important which may positively affect children's psychology. Because children who have psychological problems cannot be satisfied from life like other children who are living with continuous family. For instance, in the 2000th year Amato analysed that children from divorced families tend to obtain less educational achievements and are less interested in studies. It is followed that psychological disorders from childhood have consecutive effects for children's future because of parental divorce.

Argument #3 Financial problems on parental divorced families' children.

Financial problems are most seen issue in divorced families' half. It is challenging for their children. It has negative effects for those children's future. Money is a necessary need for children's education. Of course it is not a problem in all families however in some cases fathers do not pay till their children's 18 years old. For instance, it is seen that one in five divorced women fall into poverty difficulties as a result of divorce. Three out of four divorced mothers don't receive full payment of child support and the most interesting thing is five out of six children live with their mothers after divorce. It is clear from these statistics that children have problems with finance. They can feel themselves afraid of life when they want something which is available for children who are living with a full family. Furthermore, it is difficult for mothers to provide their children with health insurance with child support payment.

- **Warrant (Evidence)**

According to Biblarz (2000) children from divorced families are less likely to finish high schools and colleges because of financial difficulties. It is followed that children suffer to get diplomas because of parental divorce. In 2013 McLanahan, T. and Schneider mentioned that divorce adversely affects a variety of children's outcomes, including educational attainment. Due to the arguments of professors it is clear that parental divorce has a significant negative impact for the children's future education.

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- **Why does this matter?**

One of the main reasons to ban divorce is financial problems on children's education or other financial demandable things. Surely, by banning the divorce, we can fight against illiteracy and improve the quality of education in society and provide the young generation financially for needed sources. It will be fair if children do not face difficulties because of parental decisions.

- **Argument #4 Infection**

It is observed that nowadays the number of infected people throughout the world is becoming a significant problem. It is followed that numerous infected people are the reason to ban the divorce. At the moment, many people in the world suffer from infectious diseases that are usually transmitted through human interactions with another person, and it is known that more than 30 types of bacteria, viruses and parasites are transmitted sexually. syphilis, gonorrhea, chlamydia and trichomoniasis, HIV and human papillomavirus (HPV) have a large number of infected people and among these people you can find people who are married and from this we can conclude that if we prohibit divorces, then many of the above diseases will decrease at times, maybe even more. In the world after divorces, people usually look for a sexual partner or marry another person under such circumstances, during sexual intercourse, various infectious diseases, bacteria or viruses can pass. And for example, you can compare two states in one of which divorce is permitted and in the other it is forbidden to get divorced.

- **Warrant (evidence)**

In fact, one of the most common diseases is AIDS (HIV) AND THIS IS A GREAT PROBLEM that needs to be combated. In the fight against the problem, a ban on divorce can be important solution for that. Actually, according to the World bank , about 95.5 million people live in Vietnam, and imagine that about 211.71 thousand people in this state suffer from AIDS. According to aidsdatahub, this is 0.22% of the country's population, despite the fact that it is allowed to divorce in Vietnam. and now let's look at the neighboring country of the Philippines, where divorce is illegal, the population of the Philippines is about 110 million people according to world bank , and about 97 thousand people live in this country who have AIDS according to unaids, which is about 0.09% of the total population of the Philippines.

- **Impact (why this matter)**

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If you look at the review of one unhealthy family in which both partners are sick with incurable diseases or having any infections, in our case it is a husband or wife, then it is more likely that after divorces they may have other sexual partners and transmit or become a carrier of one or another the disease they have. if we prohibit divorcing, then the number of cases can be shortened several times, as we see in the example of the Philippines, they banned divorce and their statistics are 2 times less for AIDS patients in a neighboring country in which divorce is allowed. and from this it is possible to draw conclusions about the fact that if divorce is prohibited in Uzbekistan, then this will have a decisive role in reducing incurable diseases. Many may ask how the above diseases can multiply if they are transmitted only through sexual or intimate relationships, the answer in this case may be prostitution. Prostitutes, as a rule, are girls in need of money, if after a divorce a woman and a child do not take money for personal expenses, then this can cause corruption in a woman and under these circumstances she will have one of the diseases, then this person will become the spread of this infection, and it will be beneficial for us to prohibit divorce .

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